

**THE IMPORTANCE OF READING IN LEARNING ENGLISH
LANGUAGE**

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Abstract. This article discusses the significance of reading skills in learning English as a foreign language and suggests some ways to promote reading skills. It discusses the reasons of importance of reading skill and highlights the benefits of reading skill instruction for all levels. This article also presents two different types of reading which are useful for students' overall comprehension. Extensive reading is reading for fun and enjoyment while the intensive reading is searching some specific detail, or remembering some information and answering the question at the same time. The article concludes by presenting some ways of improving reading skills.

Key words: reading, reading comprehension, extensive reading, intensive reading, improve reading, reading speed, receptive skill.

As we know, nowadays the number of people who are learning English is increasing year by year. Well, the first reason in my mind is that this language is easy to learn for everybody when we compare it to other ones. As I am a teacher, my students often ask me how they can improve their English. Obviously, it is fact that they can improve by communicating with others, listening to podcasts or watching movies. But my initial suggestion is that they should read more and more books and understand them at the same time. Reading is the one of the four skills people should develop. It is helpful and contributes to develop other skills, for example fluency in speaking and writing abilities.

We know that it can be so boring just picking up a new English novel and reading it loudly or it may be an interesting online article. But it is not like that. It must be

something in student's level and attractive for them. Our mind is formed that it does not like boring things. So people should choose topics that they like. After they have finished one grade, they can move on to the next level. By doing that they can learn more extensive English words and they can freely express their ideas confidently. Perhaps you like reading mini stories or mini novels that are suitable for your level, whatever it is you should be a little bit more hard-working because it takes time to improve this skill, but it pays off at the end.

What it is reading and why it is such a crucial English Language skill?

Reading has been found highly beneficial for students in all levels. Reading is the receptive skill, that means while you are reading something you will receive information. Skills are divided into two types: receptive and productive skills. Receptive skills include listening and reading. Reading is a very helpful because it contributes to improve other skills in its own way, for example, grammar, vocabulary and writing. Reading can allow language learner to find their own interests and deal with them.

Find something that interests you

In my view, I love reading articles which are related to psychology, for example why people lie to each other or why should people sleep eight hours a day. After you have finished these kinds of articles you can imagine and you can give your own points. Certainly, you can choose whatever you want from any sites or internet. You can read about things that interest you are meaning for you in some way given your life experiences. Humans are created complex, maybe they do not want something is too ordinary, everything should be different. We have different viewpoints and opinions about only one thing. We also differ regarding language, culture and friends. So knowing the language, especially English language can open the doors these kinds of colorfulness in today's world. Because people are so eager to find about other cultures and also reading can open so many closed doors to people for communication and contact.

Reading is the process of looking at the series of written symbols and understanding from them. Reading can be silent (without making any noise, in our head) or aloud (so that other people can hear). Reading is a receptive skill – because while we are reading something we can receive information. But it is a complex process because at the same time we can perform two tasks: receiving information and transmitting it (even if only to ourselves). So how can reading improve our English? Well, from my point of view, if we look at some native speakers they cannot even read and write their names properly or they cannot spell words correctly but they can speak in English more fluently than us. But is it possible? Because they receive any information in English and they communicate and interact with others in English language so they do not have to improve reading skills. But you are a non-native speaker that means you should improve that skill because that is your native language. Reading is therefore a highly valuable skill and activity, it is suggested that English learners try to read as much as possible and they can develop that skill on their own and that greatly broadens their vocabulary, thus helping them in speaking and writing skills.

Reading is divided into two types: extensive reading and intensive reading. In extensive reading students can read something that is too easy, enjoyable, engaging books in order to increase their reading speed and fluency. There are some benefits of extensive reading, it can give students chances to read longer pieces of reading, which they select any kind of book that they want and they are not forced to increase their speed, and they read at their own speed. If they choose Graded books, for example stories or novels, that would be very useful for them. In extensive reading learners can build up their own vocabulary storage, When they read a lot of written texts, they will come across thousands of words and lexical units and collocations. Extensive reading helps learners to understand grammar better because students meet many grammatical structures in textbooks, they do not need to learn them in certain kind of grammatical books they can acquire them in real contexts. Extensive reading helps learners to build speed

and reading fluency. Reading speed is important because it helps learners to understand the information faster and better.

In intensive reading students pay more attention to the facts and details and they should understand the text in depth. This type of reading requires attention and focus in order to understand the meaning of the text. Intensive reading is much more useful in exams and used in them more often in order to identify students' knowledge about one theme. But apart from that, it is a powerful tool because it can help a child to improve their reading skills. It can develop a better understanding of a text, as well as their fluency and comprehension. Intensive reading is so useful for students who are struggling with reading because it makes them to read faster and remember the information at the same time. It can also improve their writing skills.

WAYS OF IMPROVING READING SKILLS:

Reading is a complex skill as it takes time to improve it, it does happen during the whole night sometimes we need to work on it if we want to be a master in it. So there are some tips and suggestions and a variety of ways how we can make it easier and more enjoyable for us.

You should set aside time to read each day

Reading can develop within the framed time and it ultimately takes practice. You can set aside 20-25 minutes each day to read. You can read anything you want within that time, for example a novel that you like or any article, fiction or whatever you want, however, you should not stop that practice.

Apply what you read by summarizing

After you have finished one text or such as a novel, you should write your own ideas about them, by doing so you can improve your memorizing. Summarizing makes you to remember some certain details and the central topics about what you read in your own words and through your own perspective. You can describe what you read for somebody or you can write a short summary about it.

Take notes while you read

Another method of improving your reading is that you should take notes while you are reading something. It maybe the important date, or the specific name of something. Additionally, you can write down the words you do not know in the notebook. Vocabulary is most important aspect for improving reading skills, because without vocabulary we do not comprehend anything even the small clauses.

In conclusion, reading is a skill that a person can read, comprehend, interpret and transmit written language or texts. Reading skills are highly beneficial in workplaces because people can understand the letters and emails better and faster. So students are learning English language they should develop this skill and focus on more attentively, because it can in turn will be helpful to develop other skills. Reading is mainly constructed by words so that they should learn new words at the first place and then choose something in their level. As you develop your reading skills, your communication and overall ability to interact with others and perform in your career can develop as well.

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